

Management of Capital Construction Investment Capital from the State Budget in Vietnam

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Abstract:

The objective of the article is to review the theoretical basis of capital construction investment capital and capital construction investment capital from the state budget. Since then, the author analyzes the situation in the Vietnamese context, the management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget in the theoretical aspect.

Keywords: Capital construction investment capital, Vietnam

1. Introduction

In the face of industrialization and modernization, the capital construction investment capital from the state budget has played an important role than ever. Therefore, the management of capital construction investment is more meaningful, because it determines the efficiency of the capital that the state budget spends for investment.

In recent years, capital construction investment capital and issues related to the management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget are attracting a lot of attention from leaders, managers, researchers and of all society. Because capital construction investment is a major and very important part of the entire national investment capital; accounting for a large proportion of the total annual state budget expenditure. Its important role is not only for the socio-economic fields but also in the field of defense - security in accordance with the country's goal of industrialization and modernization.

New policies and regimes on investment and capital construction and spending norms have been issued along with the implementation of procedures for management and control of capital construction investment expenditures of state budget capital through the State Treasury. contributing to effective spending management, saving, limiting wrong expenses, many projects completed and put into use effectively.

2. Literature review

2.1. Capital construction investment from the state budget

In fact, the phrase: "Capital construction investment" (capital construction investment) is used quite commonly. However, up to now, in the legal documents of the State, only in Decree 385 / HDBT of November 7, 1990 of the Council of Ministers on the Regulation on basic construction management has a general definition. Regarding capital construction investment capital: "Capital construction investment capital is all expenses spent to achieve investment purposes, including: investment preparation, designing and construction expenses, procurement, installation of machinery and equipment and other Other expenses are recorded in the total cost estimate".

From the explanation of the phrase of capital construction investment mentioned above, it is possible to understand capital construction investment capital from the state budget on two angles: (i) on the scope of state budget spending and (ii) on the scope of a capital construction investment project from the state budget.

- On the scope of State budget expenditure: Capital construction investment from the state budget source can be understood as the total state budget expenditure on capital construction investment approved by the competent authority in the budget year. That is the total annual capital expenditure budget approved by the National Assembly and assigned by the Prime Minister an annual state budget estimate to the ministries and boards; Central branches and local governments implement in the budget year. That is the annual plan (state budget estimate). In addition to the annual state budget estimation plan, according to the Law on Public Investment and the State Budget Law, the capital construction investment capital plan is also formulated and implemented according to the medium-term plan (3-5 years).

- On the scope of a public investment project using state budget

If considered on an investment project, the capital construction investment capital from the state budget is the total capital implemented in the order of capital construction investment, from the cost for the planning,

formulation and evaluation of investment policies and investment projects (stage of investment preparation). from); stage of implementation of investment project to handover and use stage. The total cost mentioned above is limited to the total approved investment.

2.2. Management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget

Management is a term and has many different concepts and understandings: management is the activity of one or several people impacting on their work to produce good results; management is the activities performed to get the job done; management is the effective coordination of work between a group of people or organizations together ... Combining the above understandings, with common sense, common sense is management's purposeful, yes impact organization of the management subject on the object and object managed in order to make the most effective use of the system's potentials and opportunities to achieve the set objectives in the changing environment.

The management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget is an important part of state management in the field of capital construction investment, of which the State plays the role of managing entity. However, management is subjective will, but must conform to objective laws and put in specific historical conditions for effective management. According to the above analysis, the management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget consists of the following basic constituent elements:

- Managing subjects are state agencies and units with a certain organizational structure, functions and tasks of managing capital construction investment capital from the state budget as decentralized; including macro management is the management of the State; Micro management is the management of the investor body with capital construction investment capital from the state budget.

+ The functional agencies of the State, performing the State management according to their assigned functions such as: The National Assembly promulgates the Law, the Resolutions on management of capital construction investment spending plans from the State budget; The Government promulgates Decrees, Decisions and assigns State budget expenditure estimates according to the medium-term and annual plans; The Ministry of Planning and Investment manages investment plans and allocates investment capital; Ministry of Construction manages technical, construction quality; Ministry of Finance manages payment, controls payment and finalizes investment capital ...

+ The person competent to decide on investment, is the legal representative of organizations, state agencies or enterprises, depending on investment capital.

+ Investor is the owner of the capital, the borrower or the person responsible for direct management and use, to make investment in accordance with law.

+ The funding agency, which grants capital at the request of the investor, makes direct payment to the contractor. Particularly for the armed forces, due to their specific nature and to ensure confidentiality, a number of projects under the Ministry of Public Security and the Ministry of Public Security are allocated and controlled through the financial and vertical systems of these two ministries. .

+ Contractors are sellers of products to the State. A project may have one or many contractors, such as consultancy contractors, who provide investors with project consultancy services, design, construction quality supervision ...; contractors supplying machinery, equipment and supplies; construction contractor ...

- The object of management is the entire process of distributing and using the state budget for capital construction investment; including capital planning, allocation of payment of investment capital and settlement of capital construction investment capital; or managing expenses for investment preparation, making investment and putting capital construction works into operation and use; or the object of management is the expenditure on construction, equipment procurement, other expenses ... from the budget of capital construction investment levels.

- The purpose of management is to ensure that the capital construction investment capital from the state budget is used to the right subjects, the right targets, the right plans, the right sources of capital ... to be economical, efficient, avoiding loss and waste in order to meet requirements. The best of the country's socio-economic development.

- Environment and organizational conditions: make clear to the questions what management situation is; how to manage it. Managing subjects must organize and closely manage before, during and after the allocation of capital construction investment capital from the state budget; management subjects use organizational methods, administrative methods, economic methods ... to manage. The method of managing capital construction investment capital from the state budget is the overall way of deliberate impacts of state management agencies on the object of management, in order to achieve the objectives of managing capital construction investment capital from the state budget. .

Commonly used management methods include: administrative methods, economic methods and advocacy methods, in which each management method has specific advantages and limitations.

- Management tools are mechanisms and policies promulgated by the State by laws, by-laws, planning schemes, planning maps; estimates, construction drawing designs; financial and accounting regimes; norm standards; invoices, vouchers and other relevant documents ...

The tool for managing capital construction investment capital from the state budget is a total of tangible and intangible means used by state agencies to affect the management object. The State implements the management of capital construction investment capital by establishing a legal and disciplined system so that relevant subjects can use it as a basis for implementation. The legal system is a factor of the macro environment, playing a very important role in economic management in general and the management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget in particular. In order to achieve the effectiveness of the management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget, it is necessary to have a system of appropriate legal management tools.

From the above analysis, it is possible to draw conclusions: Managing capital construction investment capital from the state budget is the operation of the management entity through the use of management methods and tools that affect the management object. The process of distributing and using capital construction investment capital from the state budget to control the capital construction investment activities effectively to achieve the goals of the State.

2.3. Characteristics of managing capital construction investment capital from the state budget

Management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget has the following main characteristics:

- Management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget must not only comply with the State Budget Law but also the Public Investment Law; Construction Law, Bidding Law, Land Law, Commercial Law ... and legal documents, regulations on capital construction investment. Because the capital construction investment capital from the state budget is the national capital source, contributed by the entire people and assigned to the State for management, the more and more the State has the responsibility to manage it closely, and must be institutionalized by the system. system of legal documents.

- Management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget must strictly comply with the operation process of capital construction investment according to Figure 2.1 on the order of execution of public investment projects, vertically and horizontally management (sub-section 2.1 .2.1). Because capital construction products have a long production time, are influenced by many natural factors, the management must follow a certain process; otherwise, it will hinder investment in capital construction and cause waste and national financial resources.

- Subjects involved in managing capital construction investment capital from the state budget are diverse, including state agencies and organizations from the central to local levels, which are decentralized and assigned to manage capital construction investment capital from the state budget. Each agency manages at a stage in the capital management process, specifically:

+ Planning and investment agencies are responsible for managing short-term and medium-term planning, allocating capital plans according to annual state budget estimates.

+ The State Treasury shall control and control the payment and settlement of capital construction investment accounts from the state budget.

+ Finance agency is responsible for managing payment, advance capital and settlement of

investment capital.

+ Investment decider is the head of the agency, organization or unit responsible to the State for management of assigned investment capital. The investment decider is responsible for allocating sufficient capital according to the project implementation schedule from the beginning to the final settlement of the completed project.

+ The investor has the function of assisting the investment decider in managing and using capital in accordance with the principle, the right purpose of capital use and the prescribed norm.

Management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget is relevant and throughout all stages and steps of the project from the planning guidelines, investment policies, making investment reports, approving public construction investment projects. submission and approval of technical designs, cost estimates, ground clearance, bidding, advance payment, payment, acceptance and hand-over, putting them into use for making and verifying and approving the settlement of completed investment projects. In management of capital construction investment capital, an important and decisive step to the efficiency of management of capital construction investment capital is the step of allocating capital plans into the investment portfolio. Because if included in the portfolio of unsuitable projects will cause serious loss and waste to the state budget.

- The objective of managing capital construction investment capital from the state budget is to ensure the use of capital for the right purposes, in accordance with the principles, standards and regulations. For capital construction investment capital from the state budget, the efficiency is not only a simple economic effect but also a synergy and socio-economic efficiency.

2.4. Principles for management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget

Capital construction investment capital from the state budget is made by non-refundable allocation to ensure capital to invest in projects requiring investment in socio-economic infrastructure, national defense and security ... ; thereby creating the necessary technical infrastructure for the comprehensive and balanced development of the national economy.

Capital construction investment capital from the state budget includes domestic capital of the state budget levels, foreign loans of the Government and foreign aid capital for the Government, authorities at all levels and state agencies. Capital construction investment capital from the state budget may be used only to allocate payments for projects funded by the state budget capital under the provisions of the State Budget Law.

The order of investment and construction is the order of stages and work steps in each stage of the process of investment and construction of each work. Investment projects, regardless of their sizes and capital levels, must strictly follow the order of investment and construction, including 4 stages: planning, investment preparation, investment execution, construction completion. put the project into operation. Jobs in the stage of investment implementation and completion of construction and use of works may be carried out sequentially or overlapping, depending on the specific conditions of each investment project. (according to the diagram 2.1 above)

The state budget investment capital for works and projects is determined in the annual state budget plan based on the socio-economic development plan of the entire national economy, capital construction plan of each ministry, branch, localities, grassroots units and the ability of the state budget capital. Therefore, managing and allocating capital construction investment capital of the state budget in accordance with the right purposes and plans to comply with the principle of state budget management and ensure the planning and balance of the entire national economy, of each state. industry, sector and locality.

The principle of management and provision of capital construction investment capital for the right purposes and in the plan requires constant improvement of the method of allocation of payment capital in the direction that the volume of completed capital construction is allocated with payment capital being medium-sized commodity products. valid and moderate to use. Improving the efficiency of capital construction investment of the national economy in general and the efficiency of capital construction investment by the state budget in particular requires the planning task to be one step ahead, constantly improving the quality of the

planning work, preparation and approval of capital construction plans.

Capital construction products have large investment capital, long construction time, complex technical structures. Management and funding according to the level of actual volume of completion of the plan in order to ensure capital for the capital construction investment process is carried out continuously in accordance with the schedule, closely check the quality of each capital construction volume and quality. the amount of completed works, ensuring that the invested capital is used for the right purposes and has adequate supplies, stagnant and causing loss and waste of investment capital.

2.5. Requirements and bases for managing capital construction investment capital from the state budget

Projects preparing for investment, must be included in the approved list, in accordance with the planning, on the basis of investment preparation estimates approved by competent authorities.

New investment projects must be approved by competent authorities before October 31, before the planning year.

Transitional projects must have adequate investment procedures and base on the implementation schedule to record capital plan targets closely.

Allocating and disbursing capital construction investment capital must on the basis of strictly implementing the sequence of capital construction investment projects, this principle ensures the planning and efficiency of capital construction investment.

Capital construction investment capital must be allocated according to the actual contents and completed volumes within the approved value estimates and capital plans. This is to ensure the disbursement for the right purpose and the right value of the project.

Allocating and disbursing capital construction investment capital must conduct control and inspection of capital-using activities; The inspection must cover the entire investment process starting from the stage of investment planning and ending with the use of fixed assets created and carried out on the basis of the principles of capital disbursement of capital construction investment. Implement this principle to promote the rational, proper use and right use of capital.

Construction works using state budget capital after being completed must perform the settlement of construction investment capital.

The settled investment capital is the entire lawful expense made in the investment process to put the work into operation. Lawful expenses are those made within the approved projects, designs and cost estimates, including adjustments and supplements according to the signed contracts and law provisions. For works using the State budget capital, the approved investment capital settlement must be within the total investment limit approved by competent authorities.

3. Contents of management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget

Investment capital formed from any source must be managed strictly, especially for capital construction investment capital from the state budget, which accounts for a large proportion of the state budget expenditure. Management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget includes a lot of contents, simultaneous works and related to many levels, many branches, agencies and units. Management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget from the perspective of financial management associated with the management of the state budget cycle includes the following basic contents:

- Planning, verifying the allocation of capital construction investment capital;
- Manage costs, advance and payment of completed volumes;
- Handling of investment capital;
- Inspecting, examining and auditing capital construction investment capital.

3.1. Planning, verifying allocation of capital construction investment

Planning investment activities plays a very important role in the management and use of investment capital. Good investment planning will be an important basis for directed, balanced investment, avoiding overlapping investment, lack of synchronism and waste of the country's resources.

The process and time for making, submitting, approving and assigning annual capital construction investment plans, for investment projects funded with the state budget capital, shall be carried out according to

the following process:

Step 1 - Instructions to set up and notify the test number

Based on the Prime Minister's directives, the Circular guides and notifies the inspection number on the budget estimates of the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Planning and Investment, ministerial-level agencies, local People's Committees, and implement announce the inspection number on the budget estimate and guide the attached investor units, make medium-term plans for capital construction investment.

Step 2 - Making, summarizing and submitting plan for approval.

Investors of projects using capital construction investment capital from the state budget shall base themselves on the project implementation schedule and objectives and elaborate capital plans of the projects and send them to superior management agencies. The superior managing agency of the investor is responsible for summing up the capital construction investment capital plans of the investors in the state budget estimate, according to the provisions of the State Budget Law.

The ministries and provincial / municipal People's Committees shall sum up and elaborate capital construction investment capital plans from the state budget and send them to the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Planning and Investment.

On the basis of the socio-economic development plan, the main balances of the economy, the Ministry of Planning and Investment and the Ministry of Finance shall actively consolidate and report to the Prime Minister and submit to the National Assembly for decision. assigning plans and investment capital to ministries and provinces.

Step 3 - Allocate, verify and notify the plan.

- The ministries shall allocate investment capital plans for each project, under their management, which fully meets the prescribed conditions, ensuring that they are in line with the assigned norms for the total investment; capital structure; capital levels of important projects of the State and in line with the Resolution of the National Assembly and the Government's guidance on the administration of the annual state budget estimate plan.

- People's Committees at all levels formulate the plan of capital allocation and submit it to the People's Council of the same level for decision. According to the Resolution of the People's Council, the People's Committee allocates and decides the allocation of investment capital plans, for each project under its management that meets all the prescribed conditions, ensuring that they are in line with the assigned norms. investment; capital structure. The Department of Finance is responsible for cooperating with the Department of Planning and Investment to estimate the allocation of investment capital for each project, managed by the province or city, before reporting it to the People's Committee for decision.

- For projects managed by the ministries: The Ministry of Finance shall verify the capital allocation plan, ensure the above capital allocation principles, notify the list and the capital of the projects that have sufficient investment procedures. and ensure regulations on capital allocation conditions for each ministry, and send to the State Treasury as a basis for capital payment control. In case of improper allocation according to regulations, the Ministry of Finance shall issue a written request to the ministries for readjustment.

- For projects managed by the province or district: Based on the investment capital plan decided by the People's Committee, the provincial and district finance agencies shall consider the construction investment procedures of the projects and notify the branches. within the province, district, and send to the State Treasury as a basis for capital payment control.

- Investors must send to financial agencies at all levels, the basic documents of the projects in the plan to verify and notify the list of capital payment of investment projects (these documents only send one times until the project finishes investment, except for cases where additions or adjustments are required, including:

+ For planning projects: the decision approving the outline, or tasks of the planning project and cost estimates for the planning work.

+ For investment preparation projects: deciding to approve cost estimates, for investment preparation work.

+ For projects implementing investment: Decision on approval of work construction investment project

(or economic - technical report for project only making economic - technical report) with investment decision. of the competent authorities, decisions on project adjustment (if any), decisions on approval of basic designs (for projects with 2-step and 3-step designs) and decisions on technical design approval (for projects with 3-step designs) or decisions approving construction drawing designs (for projects with 1-step and 2-step designs) and decisions approving total cost estimates.

- Periodically, ministries and localities shall review the implementation progress and investment objectives of the projects in the year to adjust investment capital plans according to their competence, or submit to the Prime Minister for adjustment of investment capital plans. investment and transfer of capital from projects that are unable to be implemented to projects that are performed ahead of schedule, and are still in arrears in volume, projects are likely to exceed the plan in the year.

- Before sending the plan to adjust the investment capital of each project to the finance agency, the ministries and localities shall work with the State Treasury to determine the capital amount of the annual plan already paid for the project, the excess amount of capital due to failing to implement, ensuring that the plan of the project after adjustment is not lower than the amount of State Treasury paid.

- If after adjustment, there is still excess capital compared to the assigned plan, the surplus capital shall be adjusted for other units under decisions of competent authorities.

The deadline for adjusting the annual investment capital plan to end is December 31 of the plan year.

3.2. Cost management, advance and payment of completed volumes

- Management of construction costs: inspecting and supervising the application of norms and unit prices to ensure compliance with regulations on job composition, technical requirements, construction conditions and construction measures, With the regulations guiding the adjustment of norms, estimated unit prices and regimes in capital construction management of the State and localities, attention should be paid to the validity duration of documents.

- Management of equipment costs: managing the equipment list, quantity, types, capacity, technical specifications, etc. to ensure the right content of equipment investment in the approved project. Next, it is necessary to closely monitor and monitor to ensure that these machines and equipment are used for the right purposes, exploited and utilized effectively.

- Management of consultancy expenses and other expenses: for consultancy jobs or jobs already included in the consultancy expense norms promulgated by the State, based on the norms of each job content to be checked. investigation and supervision; In case the job content is not included in the set norms, the estimate shall be made to determine the costs or to apply the cost levels of similar projects and constructions already implemented.

*** Advance management**

- For investment projects, or workloads of investment projects, which are granted advance payment, the State Treasury will advance advance capital to beneficiaries and gradually recover the advance capital upon payment of block amount of work completed.

- According to the progress of the project, after the construction contract takes effect and the hirer has received the advance payment guarantee, the contractor is given advance funding to carry out the work of the contract. The advance capital level, time of advance payment and recovery of advances must be agreed upon by the parties in the contract.

- The advance level is specified in the contracts within the minimum and maximum limits according to the contract value and must not exceed the annual capital plan already allocated to the work. In special cases, the advance payment at a higher level must be permitted by the investment decider.

- For the ground clearance work, the advance capital level according to the implementation schedule in the ground clearance plan. Units must allocate sufficient capital for site clearance.

- In addition to the maximum amount of advance capital under the above-mentioned contracts, for a number of components, semi-finished products in construction with great value must be manufactured in advance to ensure the construction schedule and some kinds of supplies. must reserve according to season, advance capital level according to necessary needs and be agreed upon by investors with contractors.

- The advance payment is recovered through the times of payment for the completed volume of the contract, which is initiated from the first payment, the level of each installment is agreed upon in detail by the two parties. withdraw when the payment for completed volume reaches 80% of contract value.

* Managing the payment of completed capital construction volumes

Investment capital payment is the investor's payment to the contractor when the completed work volume. Investment capital payments may be paid according to the construction time, may be paid according to the prescribed period or reasonable technical stops, may be paid according to the completed capital construction volume, or by items. works completed. The choice of which payment method is subject to the actual conditions of each period, the capital capacity of the investor and contractor. The problem is to harmonize the interests of investors and contractors. As a general rule, the shorter the term of payment, the more benefits for both parties to ensure the completion of the acceptance, the better the capital of both the construction contractors and the construction progress. construction.

3.3. Settlement of completed capital construction investment capital

The settlement may take place after the whole project, the work is completed, or for projects with many construction items, that each item, or each group of work items when completed, if poisonous. establish the operation and use and deem it necessary, the competent authorities approve the settlement, may allow the settlement of items (or group of items) including construction and installation costs, equipment and other related expenses. direct reference to the above item (or group of items). After the project is completed, the investor must finalize the entire project and allocate other general expenses for each project item according to regulations.

Settled investment expenses are all lawful expenses made in the course of construction investment for putting a project into operation and use. Legal expenses are all of the expenses implemented within the approved project, design and cost estimates; the signed contract (for work performed under the contract) including the adjustment and supplement approved under regulations and according to its competence. The settled investment expenses must be within the limit of the approved total investment or readjusted according to the provisions of law.

- Settlement helps to fully and accurately determine the total amount of capital invested in construction of works, investment capital converted into fixed assets, movable assets, or expenses not converted into assets of works, creating a basis for determine responsibilities of investors and investment owners in management and use of capital construction investment capital.

- Settlement of capital construction investment capital can clearly identify the quantity, quality, production capacity and value of newly increased fixed assets brought about by the investment, so as to have a plan for timely mobilization and use and promotion of the badge. results of newly completed capital construction works.

- Settlement of capital construction investment capital assessing the results of the capital construction investment process, from which the parties, especially the investor, can draw experience, in order to improve the use efficiency and enhance the management. The investment capital is in line with the current situation.

- The settlement of capital construction investment capital of a project must meet the following two basic requirements:

+ Settlement of investment capital must be correct, that is, it is necessary to identify legal capital already implemented. The settled investment capital must be determined according to the right formation source and must be taken into account the time value of money, that is, the investment capital must be determined over the years and converted into value at the time of handover. works into use. Correctly determine the investment capital converted into fixed assets, working assets, or non-assets expenses of the project; correctly determine the production capacity, the value of new fixed assets increases due to investment.

+ Settlement of investment capital must be timely. Timeliness ensures the determination of the value of fixed assets put into production and timely use in order to well manage such fixed assets, accurately determining the value of depreciation and enhancing economic accounting. On the other hand, the timeliness in the final settlement contributes to the easy and quick detection of the project's illegal costs to eliminate, avoid

negative phenomena, and streamline the investment process.

In order to ensure the two correct and timely requirements as mentioned above, there must be clear and specific provisions, contents, requirements for the settlement of investment capital, and the organizational structure for perform the settlement. At the same time, it is required to make a public final settlement to create conditions for all officials in the investor's agency, the supervising agency, the contractors, the agencies to grant and lend capital, the State management agency and all people participate in supervising the project investment process.

- Scope and subjects of making the final settlement report include:

+ All capital construction projects, irrespective of the scale, form of construction, investment capital sources and management levels, when completed and put into production and use, investors shall have to make final settlement. the set of capital construction investment capital of the construction work shall be completed with the investment managing agency and the agency allocating capital construction investment capital.

+ If the project is invested with many capital sources, the investor must make a total final settlement of the whole project, including separate settlement according to the structure of each capital source already used for capital construction investment when starting the preparatory work. investment, starting construction and put into production and use.

+ In the course of work construction, if each work item is completed and handed over for use right from the end of construction of each such item, the investor must fully determine capital construction investment capital (including calculated amounts) into new increased properties of such work item, reported to the investment managing agency, the issuing agency or the lending capital for investment as a basis for settlement and discussion. delivery, accounting and use management of the unit receiving assets. The settlement of capital construction investment capital may be finalized for each work item and the total settlement of the entire project after project completion.

- The settlement contents include:

+ Determining the total actual capital invested in the work, including construction and installation expenses, equipment procurement expenses and other basic construction expenses;

+ Determination of damage expenses not calculated into the work's value;

+ Determination of the total actual investment capital calculated into investment projects: this capital amount is equal to the total actual capital invested in the construction of works minus the damage expenses not included in the value of the works;

+ Determination of value and classification of fixed assets and mobile assets brought about by investment, including:

. Investment capital is considered to be converted into fixed assets according to the State's regulations, including: construction and installation expenses, equipment procurement expenses and other basic construction expenses counted into the value of works (allocated to each fixed asset). The total value of all fixed assets mentioned above is the value of fixed assets of the whole work.

. The allocation of capital of other basic construction expenses (including investment preparation expenses) to each fixed asset is shown on the principle: that expenses directly related to certain fixed assets are calculated directly for that fixed asset, the The general expenses related to many fixed assets of a work are allocated according to the proportion of capital of such fixed assets accounted for the total investment capital of the works.

+ Determining fully the value of fixed assets and movable assets of capital construction works transferred to other units for management and use to account the reduction of investment capital for the works and increasing capital for the using units.

- In order to match the fluctuation of prices, when the construction is completed and the works are put into production and use, the settlement of the works must be reflected according to two prices:

+ Actual price of capital construction investment used annually;

+ Converted price on the time of handing over and putting the works into production and use (the conversion is under the guidance of the Ministry of Construction).

3.4. Inspecting, examining and auditing capital construction investment capital from the state budget

* Objectives of the inspection work to inspect the management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget to:

+ Detecting and concluding irregularities in the observance of the order and procedures for capital construction investment, the application of norms, unit prices and acceptance of the final settlement of completed capital construction volumes, the settlement of investment capital and discussion Assigning works to put into use.

+ Determining the cause of violations and assigning specific responsibilities to individuals and collectives related to detected violations.

+ Proposing and proposing solutions to rectify, rectify and handle violations and propose amendments and supplements to mechanisms and policies related to the management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget.

* Basic contents for inspection and examination of the management of capital construction investment capital from the state budget include:

- Check the observance of the order and procedures on capital construction:

+ Collecting and mastering regimes and documents on capital construction of the State and of each locality; correctly understand the order and regulations and regulations on capital construction; firmly grasping the contents and regulations on capital construction.

+ Learn investment capital (allocated from the state budget, bank loans or ODA sources). The invested capital is guaranteed, when the construction is completed, Party B will be paid in time. At the same time, the inspectors must firmly grasp the value of investment capital and problems, difficulties and advantages in implementing construction investment capital.

+ Firmly grasp the agency competent to decide on investment, the investor, the design consultancy agency, the agency approving the design, the approval of estimates, the participating Bs, the main B and the auxiliary B have sufficient real capacity. show or not.

- Examining contents of formulation, evaluation and decision of investment projects:

+ Review the implementation of investment purposes.

+ Are supplies, equipment, and product consumption reasonable?

+ Ability to raise project capital.

+ Procedures for land allocation of localities.

+ Construction location and investment scale consistent with the requirements set out.

+ Checking whether the project is carried out according to the prescribed order.

+ The agency that approves each stage of a work project has the proper authority and function.

+ Determine who the investor is? Forms of management of investment, location and land area to be used, construction design capacity, total investment capital, construction time and major construction phases.

- Checking the cost estimates that have been appraised and approved:

+ Check that the calculation and layout of cost estimates are correct and in accordance with the instructions of the Ministry of Construction or not?

+ Checking the application of fee rates such as general costs, interest rates, design survey rates depending on each specific case according to each type of construction work and the time of different construction.

+ Compare the estimation test results with the approved cost estimates to request the investors to explain and make proposals to the agencies approving the estimates.

- Checking the implementation of investment projects:

+ Investment preparation: check the implementation of land allocation or lease; inspection of site clearance and compensation costs; inspect the selection of construction survey consultants, technical experts; checking capital sources and capital recording plans, related to the solvency and settlement of completed works; check design records, cost estimates properly and reasonably or not? Detecting errors in design and cost estimates; to check whether the organization of bidding, the selection of contractors or the appointment of a contractor comply with the State regulations? inspect the procurement of major equipment in the stages of

signing sale and purchase contracts, acceptance of handover for preservation, equipment installation, sales promotion and liquidation of equipment sale and purchase contracts; check the insurance purchase, prevent the risk of the project.

+ Examining the project implementation stage: (i) Checking the content and executing contracts of contracting between the parties A, B and between main and auxiliary B with the legal person status and business license. practicing? Is the content of the contract contrary to the invitation or bid? Check the contract performance is not wrong with the terms the parties have signed it? (ii) Checking the organization of construction, supervision of volume, quality, construction techniques, author supervision according to the approved design? (iii) What are the problems between the investor, principal B, and minor B during the construction process? check work diaries and records of incident settlement and settlement of volumes arising during construction. (iv) Checking acceptance, payment, settlement, handover of works and putting the works into use within the prescribed time and procedures? Consider the implementation of depreciation. (v) Checking the appraisal and approval of the settlement of works

- Check the actual volume of completed works.

+ Checking whether the design documents have been prepared, fully approved or designed and constructed?

+ From the technical design, the calculation and peeling back of the prognosis of large volumes, high values or doubts that need to be checked which the B usually calculates as concrete weight, foundation excavation volume, construction volume, door area, tiling area, plastering, from which compared with the amount of supplies recorded in the estimate, payment slips, if the difference needs to be requested by the governing body and party B.

+ During the inspection process, if any technical absurd points are detected, it is necessary to question and request the design agency to explain.

+ The necessary large quantity or high value can be measured and recalculated the actual volume, in order to compare with the volume according to the approved design, if the investor and Party B cannot explain it properly, If it is reasonable, it is recommended that the compensation for the value of the value of the volume be null.

+ Particularly, it is necessary to pay attention to the covered sinking volumes such as the volume of excavating the foundation, dredging mud, sucking the river mud, the volume of underground piles, the volume of demolition and patching, the volume of leveling and leveling. Potholes on sides A and B often have an actual false confirmation of this volume to increase the payment value for B.

+ Checking the arising volume in addition to the approved cost estimate design, whether there is a record certifying the arising volume with plausible reasons and approved by competent agencies.

+ With the actual volume larger than the design volume, it must be additionally approved but must be lawful and valid; If the actual volume is smaller than the recognized design volume, payment shall be made only according to the actual volume.

- Checking the completed work volume:

+ By direct observation, the defects, faults such as cracked walls, broken beams, uneven plastered walls, variegated paint, tarnish, discrepant door sizes, wrong equipment and supplies, specifications compared to estimate design.

+ Checking, checking, taking over, settling, handing over works, putting the works into use on time and according to the prescribed procedures? Consider the implementation of depreciation.

+ Checking the evaluation and approval of settlement of works.

4. Conclusion

Firstly, renovating the inspection work for investment activities funded by the state budget capital: Inspection is the main function of management, especially financial management.

Secondly, simplify payment procedures, improve forms and documents, use the modern payment system, to ensure prompt settlement. It is necessary to have a flexible and flexible coordination between the State Treasury - Department of Finance and Pricing and Department of Planning and Investment, Department of Construction,

and the investor to organize training on disbursement of capital for investors, to conduct payment of capital according to the one-door regime, in accordance with the process, is open, fast and tight.

Thirdly, strengthen auditing activities for investment from the state budget. The State Audit plays an important role in the market economy. From the role of the auditor, we first need to improve the legal basis for the organization of the state audit activities as well as create favorable conditions for the State Audit to report on the final settlement of the first projects. from the state budget. If possible, audit both planned and final accounts. On the other hand, it is necessary to raise awareness and fully and seriously implement regulations on elaboration and verification of state budget estimates and state budget allocation plans. It is necessary to train auditors and build advanced and modern auditing methods and provide modern facilities for auditors.

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